

Identification Of Plants and Its Medicinal Properties Using Deep Learning

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Abstract— This study explores the application of deep learning techniques for the identification of Indian medicinal plants and leaves. The study employs three advanced convolutional neural networks—EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and Xception—to achieve high-accuracy classification of various medicinal plant species. Data for the project was obtained from the Indian Medicinal Leaves Image Datasets, which include two subsets: the Medicinal Plant dataset and the Medicinal Leaf dataset. To improve model performance and generalization, transfer learning and data augmentation methods were utilized. The training and validation of these models on the dataset demonstrated their significant efficacy in classifying medicinal plants. Among the models, Xception achieved the highest accuracy at 97%, followed by ResNet50 at 96%, and EfficientNetB0 at 90%. These results underscore the potential of deep learning in botanical research and the conservation of medicinal plant resources. The successful use of advanced CNN architectures suggests substantial benefits for the identification and classification of medicinal plants, with implications for botany, pharmacology, and healthcare. Future work will aim to expand the dataset and explore additional deep learning models to further enhance classification accuracy and robustness.

Keywords—Deep Learning, Tensor Flow, Medicinal Plants, EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, Xception, Transfer Learning, Data Augmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The identification and classification of medicinal plants play a crucial role in various fields such as botany, pharmacology, and healthcare. Traditional methods of plant classification often rely on manual observation and expertise, which can be time-consuming and prone to error. With advancements in deep learning and computer vision, there is a growing interest in leveraging these technologies to automate and enhance the accuracy of plant identification processes.

In this context, this study focuses on the application of deep learning techniques to classify Indian medicinal plants and their leaves. The use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), particularly models like EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and

Xception, offers a promising approach due to their ability to learn hierarchical features directly from image data. These models have been pretrained on large-scale

datasets and fine-tuned on specific tasks, enabling them to achieve state-of-the-art performance in image classification tasks. Data augmentation are employed. Transfer learning allows the models to leverage pre-existing knowledge from general image datasets, while data augmentation diversifies the training data by applying transformations such as flips, rotation

The datasets used in this study are sourced from the Indian Medicinal Leaves Image Datasets, which provide a comprehensive collection of images categorized into medicinal plant and leaf classes. To optimize model performance and mitigate overfitting, techniques such as transfer learning, and zooms.

The ultimate goal of this research is to develop robust models capable of accurately identifying and categorizing medicinal plants and their leaves. Such models can potentially contribute to various applications, including biodiversity conservation, herbal medicine research, and pharmaceutical development. By automating the identification process, these technologies could also facilitate the sustainable utilization and preservation of medicinal plant resources.

In summary, this study explores the integration of deep learning methodologies, specifically leveraging TensorFlow, to advance the field of botanical informatics. By combining sophisticated neural network architectures with domain-specific datasets, we aim to demonstrate the efficacy and

practical applicability of AI in the classification of Indian medicinal plants and leaves.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology section outlines the plan and methods used to conduct the study. This includes the universe of the study, sample of the study, data sources, study variables, and analytical framework. The details are as follows;

A. Population and Sample

The dataset used in this study comprises images from the Kaggle Indian Medicinal Leaves Image Datasets, which include two main subsets: the Medicinal Plant dataset and the Medicinal Leaf dataset. These datasets represent the universe of the study. The sample consists of images of various medicinal plants and leaves, which are divided into training, validation, and test sets to evaluate the performance of different convolutional neural network (CNN) models.

B. Data and Sources of Data

For this study, secondary image data has been collected from Kaggle's Indian Medicinal Leaves Image Datasets. The data includes a diverse range of images representing different medicinal plant species and their leaves. The datasets are split into training, validation, and test sets to facilitate model training and evaluation. Data augmentation techniques are applied to enhance the robustness of the models.

C. Theoretical framework

The study employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to classify medicinal plants and leaves. The dependent variable in this study is the class label of each image (medicinal plant or leaf type). The independent variables are the pixel values of the images, which are processed through the CNN models to extract features and perform classification.

The models used in this study include EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and Xception, all of which have been pre-trained on large image datasets and fine-tuned on the medicinal plant datasets. Transfer learning and data augmentation are employed to improve model performance and generalization.

D. Statistical tools and econometric models

This section elaborates on the proper statistical and analytical models used to derive inferences from the data. The details of the methodology are given as follows:

1) Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are used to summarize the characteristics of the datasets, including the number of images in each class, mean pixel values, and standard deviations. These statistics provide insights into the distribution and variability of the data, which are essential for understanding model performance and potential biases.

2) Model Training and Evaluation

The methodology for training and evaluating the CNN models involves the following steps:

1. Data Preprocessing:

Images are resized to 224x224 pixels.

Data normalization is performed to scale pixel values to the range [0, 1].

Data augmentation techniques, such as random flips, rotations, and zooms, are applied to increase the diversity of the training data.

2. Model Architecture:

EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and Xception models are used as base models with pre-trained weights.

Custom layers are added on top of these base models to perform classification specific to the medicinal plant dataset.

3. Training Procedure:

The models are trained using transfer learning, where the initial layers of the pre-trained models are frozen, and the custom layers are trained on the medicinal plant dataset.

The models are compiled using the Adam optimizer and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss.

Training is performed with an 80-10-10 split for training, validation, and testing.

4. Evaluation Metrics:

Model performance is evaluated using accuracy, loss plots, ROC curves, and confusion matrices.

Accuracy and loss plots show the training and validation performance over epochs.

ROC curves illustrate the true positive rate versus the false positive rate.

Confusion matrices provide a detailed breakdown of correct and incorrect classifications.

E. Comparison of the Models

The next step of the study is to compare these competing models to evaluate that which one of these models is more supported by data.

1) Model Comparison

The performance of the different models is compared based on the following metrics:

Accuracy: The proportion of correctly classified images.

Loss: The measure of model error during training and validation.

ROC Curve: A graphical representation of the trade-off between true positive and false positive rates.

Confusion Matrix: A table that shows the performance of the classification model by displaying the actual versus predicted classifications.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the application of deep learning models, specifically EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and Xception, in the classification of Indian medicinal plants and leaves. The Xception model achieved the highest accuracy (97%), followed by ResNet50 (96%) and EfficientNetB0 (90%). The use of transfer learning and data augmentation proved effective in improving the models.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Table 4.1: Summary of Neural Networks Used

Network	Accuracy
Xception	97
EfficientNetB0	96
ResNet50	90

The performance of the three convolutional neural network models—Xception, ResNet50, and EfficientNetB0—was evaluated on the task of classifying Indian medicinal plants and leaves. The accuracy of each model is summarized in the table above.

1) Results of Xception

Figure 1: Accuracy, Loss plots of Xception

Figure. 2 Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC) of Xception

Figure. 3 Confusion Matrix of Xception

B. Results of EfficientNetB0

Figure. 4 Accuracy, Loss plots of EfficientNetB0

Figure. 5 Receiver Operating Characteristic curve(ROC) of EfficientNetB0

Figure. 6 Confusion Matrix of EfficientNetB0

C. Results of ResNet50

Figure. 7 Accuracy, Loss plots of ResNet50

Figure. 8 Receiver Operating Characteristic curve(ROC) of ResNet50

Figure. 9 Confusion Matrix of ResNet50

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the application of deep learning models, specifically EfficientNetB0, ResNet50, and Xception, in the classification of Indian medicinal plants and leaves. The Xception model achieved the highest accuracy (97%), followed by ResNet50 (96%) and EfficientNetB0 (90%). The use of transfer learning and data augmentation proved effective in improving the models' performance. These findings suggest that advanced CNN architectures can significantly enhance the identification and classification of medicinal plants, contributing to fields such as botany, pharmacology, and healthcare. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset and exploring additional deep learning models to further improve classification accuracy and robustness.

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